

THE STATE OF ENHANCING PEDAGOGICAL INTUITION IN FUTURE FOOTBALL COACHES AT HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the attention being given to the development of football in Uzbekistan, the role of higher education institutions in this process, the teaching of football and issues of improving coaches' qualifications, as well as ways to enhance the pedagogical intuition of higher education institution students, including sports coaches. The analysis of these aspects is presented in tables.

Currently, football is one of the most popular and beloved sports in Uzbekistan, holding special significance in the field of physical education and sports. It is considered one of the sports that receive attention at the state policy level. Engaging in football contributes to the development of all physical qualities.

In Uzbekistan, attention to the development of football is steadily increasing. In this process, the role of higher educational institutions, football education, and the issue of improving coaches' qualifications are of great importance.

Higher educational institutions training specialists in the field of physical education and sports in Uzbekistan, particularly the Uzbekistan State University of Physical Education and Sports (UzSUPES), play a key role in providing highly qualified football personnel. Here, students in the football program receive:

Theoretical knowledge: Subjects such as football history, rules, tactics, psychology, and physiology are taught in depth.

Practical skills: Practical exercises are conducted on technical elements (ball reception, passing, shooting), tactical schemes, and physical training exercises.

Coaching Pedagogy: Skills are provided in the methodology of training young football players, planning and organizing training sessions.

Additionally, several pedagogical universities have faculties of physical education that train football specialists for general education schools and sports schools. The contribution of higher educational institutions to football development is evident not only in training professional football players but also in preparing qualified coaches and sports organizers for the future.

Issues of improving and developing coaches' qualifications are becoming increasingly important. Undoubtedly, the role of coaches is crucial in football development. In Uzbekistan,

serious attention is paid to improving coaches' qualifications: international exchange of experience, local seminars and training sessions, and support for young coaches are being implemented. Overall, the focus on football education in higher educational institutions and the continuous improvement of coaches' qualifications in Uzbekistan's football development will serve to train strong and competitive football players in the future, as well as lay the foundation for the national team's success in the international arena.

Methodology:

From this perspective, we analyzed the issues of developing intuition among football students in the Faculty of Physical Education and Sports at selected higher education institutions (FERSU, USWLU, ASU) to study and identify the activities of coaches.

In Uzbekistan's universities, these courses (SPMO) are implemented in accordance with the curriculum for Improving Sports Pedagogical Skills (Football). The study also examines whether the didactic conditions (type of educational institution, teaching hours, textbooks, experience of sports specialists) are sufficient or insufficient for completing the tasks in the existing curricula. Within the framework of this training program, students acquire sufficient and necessary knowledge about the development of sports in Uzbekistan and worldwide, teaching sports, and managing the process of athlete training. The subject "Theory and Methodology of Football" is taught as a leading and core specialized subject in the training of football coaches.

The purpose of the discipline: at the initial stage, it consists of training students in educational-methodological and scientific-methodological work, as well as preparing and developing the qualifications of scientific-pedagogical specialists.

The main task of the discipline is to teach the means, methods, principles of football, the organization and conduct of training sessions and competitions, football techniques and tactics, means of increasing and developing physical fitness, fundamentals of sports training, and theoretical and practical knowledge.

(SPMO) Improving Sports Pedagogical Skills (Football)

Purpose of the discipline: Within the framework of this educational program, students will acquire sufficient and necessary knowledge about the development of sports in Uzbekistan and globally, teaching sports disciplines, and managing the process of athlete training.

The subject "Theory and Methodology of Football" is taught as a leading and primary specialized subject in the training of football coaches. Basic knowledge necessary for mastering the subject "Theory of Football." Learning outcomes in terms of knowledge

Objective of the discipline: To gain knowledge about the goals and objectives of the "Methods of Teaching Football" course, the history of football's development, and the role of football in the field of physical education and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as implemented in the process of mastering the academic discipline "Improving Sports Pedagogical Skills" (football).

Must have an understanding of the fundamental aspects of football, physical qualities, physical development, and types of football;

Must know and be able to apply methods of teaching football exercises through practical movement skills and abilities.

In terms of skills:

Must possess skills in football exercise techniques, teaching football lessons at school, and planning and standardizing football training.

In the process of mastering the academic discipline "Improving Sports Pedagogical Skills" (football), students should gain knowledge about the goals and objectives of the "Methods of Teaching Football" course, the history of football's development, and the role of football in the field of physical education and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Must have an understanding of the fundamental aspects of football, physical qualities, physical development, and types of football. Must know and be able to apply methods of teaching football exercises through practical skills and abilities.

In terms of skills:

Must possess skills in football exercise techniques, teaching football lessons at school, and planning and standardizing football training.

In our opinion, to improve the pedagogical intuition of future football coaches, it is necessary to conduct exercises that develop pedagogical intuition in practical classes throughout the entire bachelor's degree program (for 4 years). The ratio of time spent on organizing initial training can remain consistent, but in the training stages aimed at developing pedagogical intuition, the time allocation can be determined based on the athletes' needs for training focused on improving pedagogical intuition.

However, we believe that practical classes designed to develop the pedagogical intuition of future football coaches in universities are not sufficiently organized.

Furthermore, the analysis of a questionnaire designed to assess the state of pedagogical intuition in future football coaches within the football departments of sports and physical education faculties in higher educational institutions revealed that due to insufficient training hours dedicated to developing coaches' pedagogical intuition, football players at the initial stage have not formed pedagogical intuition for quick decision-making, while at advanced levels, pedagogical intuition skills remain underdeveloped. It was found that some football coaches have little to no experience in making quick intuition-based decisions during training sessions. Consequently, in many cases, despite having sufficient knowledge, graduates of sports and physical education departments specializing in football lack the skills for quick decision-making, reflection, regular analysis of experiences, and pedagogical intuition in complex situations.

Conclusion: Based on this analysis, the conclusion was made that football coaches sometimes use pedagogical intuition. Based on this situation, we focused our research on the methodology for improving the pedagogical intuition of future football coaches. In order for football students of the Faculty of Physical Culture and Sports to become qualified specialists, it is recommended to effectively use pedagogical intuition in addition to textbooks, practical classes, and teaching aids, as well as to include a system of exercises and tasks that develop it.

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